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Decolonising Religious and
Moral Education in Scottish
Non-Denominational Schools

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Introduction

In the Western academy, including Scotland, decolonisation of the curriculum has proven to be an ‘uncomfortable conversation’ because it deals with unsettling truths about colonialism (subjugation, silencing, slavery, and epistemic violence) many people would rather wish it was a topic left alone (Race et al., 2022). Decolonisation is a necessary process in redressing not only the colonial past but also challenging ‘coloniality of power’ that still scripts the epistemology of knowledge in contemporary curriculum-making, including Religious and Moral Education (RME) (Quijano, 2000).

The policy brief provides the impetus to decolonise RME in Scotland in ways that aligns with ideals of epistemic equity, humanness, and social justice ensuring also that its content and delivery is anti-racist and non-discriminatory (see Matemba, 2021a; Ball, 2022; Mohammed, 2023). In Scotland, RME is offered in non-denominational school sector, historically affiliated with the Presbyterian church. A separate confessional subject called ‘Religious Education’ is offered in Catholic schools, which are also publicly funded (Stewart, 2011; Matemba, 2018).

As a statutory mandated subject and one of the eight core areas of the Scottish curriculum (Stewart, 2011; Scholes, 2022), RME must continue to be supported. In addition, RME is uniquely placed to inculcate socio-cultural/religious values and shared concerns in an increasingly diverse but religiously fractured world.

Scotland’s connection with colonialism as part of the British empire and its own complicit with the slave trade, demands decolonial reflections and actions that must inform how RME as a legislated subject in schools is framed in the curriculum and actualised in the classroom (McCarthy, 2022).

Scottish Context

Despite the 'moral claims' of being different the Scottish missionary movement was complicit in the overall British colonial empire (Mackenzie, 2008). Scotland's links to slavery (evident today in Scottish street names and public memorials) and how the Clyde shipyards facilitated the slave trade, must be part of the curriculum (Mackenzie and Devine, 2011).

Scotland has a sizeable immigrant population (i.e., 'new Scots'), including many from formerly colonised parts of the world, for example, the Caribbean and Africa (Scottish Government, 2018). The absence of an overt decolonial and anti-racist element in RME in a country historically implicated in the British colonial empire necessitates a rethink on how learners can be engaged in decolonial ways of thinking and knowing in challenging all forms of epistemological hegemony in the curriculum and classroom discourse (Mignolo, 2000).

Since the promulgation of the Scottish modern system of education in 1872, RME has existed as part of a colonial continuum in education supported by a Christonormativity guiding its conceptualisation and classroom discourse (Matemba, 2014).

The 1972 Miller Report instituted by the government to investigate the health of Religious Education (then offered as Christian Instruction) demonstrated the need urgent reform if the subject was to be relevant and survive in a modern educational context. It argued that learning about Christianity alone was "... ineffective in the genuine religious education of children" (Miller Report, 1972: 82).

The Miller Report came at a time of wider recognition of Scotland's increasing multi-racial composition and therefore the need for inclusion in the curriculum. In the general context of Ninian Smart's revolutionary ideas about the application of phenomenology in the study of religion in public schools (Smart, 1968), between the 1970s and 1980s there emerged critical scholarship in the works of Ronald Goldman, Michael Grimmitt, John Hull, Elizabeth Kinniburgh, J.W.D. Smith, and Alex Rodger challenging the conceptualisation of RME as being out of sync with educational and development needs of children (Matemba, 2014).

In addition, the work Religious Education specialist advisors stationed in each of Scotland's 32 local education authorities and influential committees such as the Scottish Joint Committee on Religious Education (SJCRE) and Association of Teachers of RE in Scotland (ATRES) provided practical suggestions in the development of inclusive content and pedagogy in RME (Scottish Office, 1994).

In response to these developments, as early as 1970s unofficially some Scottish schools had begun to include aspects of Islam, and Buddhism

to expose children to different ways of religious knowing in RME. Officially, though it was the introduction of the 5-14 Curriculum in 1994 that explicitly expected schools to teach 'other' religions although still giving Christianity a privileged status in the curriculum (Scottish Office, 1992, 1994).

The neo-confessional approach has continued to the current RME programme with the Curriculum for Excellence (CfE) introduced in 2009/10. In CfE, RME gives attention to world religions selected for study and non-religious belief systems while still maintaining a Christian neo-confessional approach on the account of history and national tradition (Scottish Government, 2009).

Methodology

The policy brief is informed by the author's critical reading of decolonial and anti-racist debate in Religious Education in recent scholarship particularly special issues in journals like Religious Education: The Official Journal of the Religious Education Association (Mercer, 2017) and British Journal of Religious Education (Gearon, et al., 2021).

Information is also drawn from the author's wider scholarly work and professional experience teaching Religious Education in schools and teacher education in Africa and Scotland for over 30 years. Further, in producing this policy brief, the author examined relevant government 'texts' (government reports, policies, and the school curriculum/syllabus) related to RME in Scotland.

Key Issues

The concern in Scotland is that despite indications of decoloniality in RME, it remains a school subject in a neo-colonial formulation. While 'decolonial glimpses' of inclusion can be seen in the attempts to expose children to other ways of religious knowing (i.e., teaching 'other' selected religions in addition to Christianity), overall Scottish RME remains bounded in a neocolonial continuum.

The continued Christian hegemony through the adoption of neo-confessional approach, continues to sustain a (neo)colonial RME curriculum. This 'neo/colonised' curriculum is framed by a selective tradition that includes certain knowledges as 'official' (e.g., normative religions) and excludes/marginalises other forms of knowledge (Matemba, 2024). The making of RME within CfE, for example, is in a neo-confessional format that must be challenged in forging a curriculum that must take a critical stance against Christianity as hegemonic knowledge in RME (Mignolo, 2000).

Christianity as hegemonic knowledge in Scottish RME is out of sync in a country whose religious outlook is heterogeneous, including minority ethnic who practice different 'home' beliefs and other spiritual manifestations. A secular Scotland but with many people following non-normative belief systems (and none) also demands epistemological humility in the framing and actualisation of RME (Maduro, 2011). Such a programme must provide an equitable space for different knowledges and counter knowledges to co-exist (Vliek, 2019).

RME in Scotland must demonstrate a commitment to being hospitable to difference (Coll, 2021), and recentring marginalised/controversial issues including how the subject must deal with structural racism, white fragility, patriarchy, sexualities (including LGBTQ1+) and non-normative worldviews, religious and none (Coll, 2021; Hess, 2017).

Decolonising RME should instruct the curriculum to include 'uncomfortable conversations' in educating learners about the country's unenviable colonial past (trauma of empire, slavery, and slave trade (see Craps. 2013; Huish, 2013). This should engender deeper debates about reparations (restitution, acknowledgement, atonement, and forgiveness), racial discrimination, and understanding the lived experiences of minority ethnic in Scotland.

How Scottish schools approach RME in practice varies with some schools following strictly the neo-confessional approach (Christianity, World Religions Selected for Study and Development of Values) while others and empowered by teacher autonomy premised in CfE take a somewhat liberal approach by choosing to teach new knowledges in the context of the school environment (i.e., localism) (Matemba, 2015, 2018).

Recommendations and Policy Implications

Since within its communities Scotland has non-indigenous peoples from formerly colonised and enslaved parts of the world (Scottish Government (2018), it is imperative to decolonise RME in ways that atones for Scotland's involvement in colonialism.

Within the legislative provision of RME (Stewart, 2011), educational policy must acknowledge the country's injurious colonial past by including content that recognises the suffering of Black people under slavery and the slave trade.

Decolonising RME must not mean erasing the colonial past per se, but rather reconstituting the subject by embedding counter-hegemonic strategies and creating decolonial spaces that ensure equity and fair treatment of different forms of knowledge (Vliek, 2019; Matemba 2021a).

Beyond strategies to decolonise RME, there is a need for policy actors, curriculum planners and educators to declare and then critically reassess their positionality (i.e., structural location) because no one engages with decolonisation as *tabula rasa*. Because positionality "... shapes how phenomena can be known, understood and constructed" (Lipscombe, et al., 2021: 5), this can impact positively or negatively knowledge-making and praxis in Scottish RME.

In its current conceptualisation, RME in Scotland fails the 'knowledge equity' litmus test because it does not embed the knowledge, expertise, and experiences of its minority ethnic (Jaffe, 2017). Further, legislative and policy rhetoric in Scottish RME privileges Christian beliefs as 'valuable' knowledge in curriculum-making and framing of RME through a neoconfessional approach (Stewart, 2011).

Epistemic equity is needed in RME by decentring Christian hegemony (in text, e.g., policy and curriculum) towards democratising knowledge-making. It is important for RME to dislodge the assumed Christian homogeneity in the way Christianity is treated in RME not only devoid of denominational difference but also treated as *primus inter pares* based on the account of history and national tradition (Matemba, 2015).

Therefore, deliberate efforts must be undertaken to open learning in RE to epistemic diversity by including knowledges of minority ethnic who have a lived experience of colonialism including racism (Norms, 2006).

The decolonial space in RME must be polyphonic where counterhegemonic discourse must take place towards epistemological transformation of knowledge children are exposed to in Scottish schools (Santos, 2018).

Scottish RME must be redesigned in ways that places reparative justice at the heart of teaching and learning (Agozino, 2021). By 'reparative justice', we mean how Scottish RME can contribute to the country's efforts towards acknowledgment, reconciliation, and atonement for the fact that also religion and education were at the epicentre of all European empires (Gearon, et al., 2021).

Educators must utilise anti-oppressive approaches in countering systemic racism, racial prejudice, and oppression on specific racial groups (Trisos, Auerbach and Katti, 2021; Mohammed, 2023). In this way the RME classroom will become a space of epistemic activism where diverse religious traditions (and none), cultural experiences and historic experiences of colonialism are central to teaching and learning (Ball, 2022; Vallejos, Levrard and Matharan, 2023).

As religion and education were central to the colonial project (Gearon et al., 2021), RME must challenge not only the historical (Christian) justification (by some) for slavery but also appraise the work of abolitionists whose efforts led to the gradual discontinuation of the slave trade (see Curley et al., 2022).

Restructuring Scottish RME will require a careful balancing act by policy actors due to conflicts over symbolic power that may exist in the social space where different agents are likely to jostle over curriculum-making in RE (Matemba, 2021b).

To ensure the successful implementation of decolonised RME in Scottish schools, teacher education and in-service opportunities must be reconfigured in line with decolonial thinking and action.

References

- Agozino, B. (2021) "Reparative justice: The final stage of decolonization," *Punishment & Society*, 23(5), pp. 613–630.
- Ball, J. (2022) "Decolonising the teaching of Jesus in English primary schools," *Journal of Religious Education*, 70, pp. 311–325.
- Coll, R. (2021) "Hospitality to difference: LGBT, religious education and the Catholic school," *Journal of Religious Education* (2021) 69(25), pp. 25–36.
- Craps, S. (2013) *Postcolonial Witnessing Trauma Out of Bounds*, London: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Curley, A., Gupta, P., Lookabaugh, L., Neubert, C. and Smith, S. (2022), "Decolonisation is a Political Project: Overcoming Impasses between Indigenous Sovereignty and Abolition," *Antipode*, 54, pp.1043–1062.
- Gearon, L., Kuusisto, A., Matemba, Y.H., Benjamin, S., Du Preez, P., Koirikivi, P. and Simmonds, S. (2021) Special Issue: Decolonising the Religious Education Curriculum: International Perspectives in Theory, Research, and Practice, *British Journal of Religious Education*, 43(1), 135pp.
- Hess, M. (2017) "White Religious Educators Resisting White Fragility: Lessons from Mystics," *Religious Education*, 112(1), pp. 46–57.
- Huish, R. (2013) "Dissent 101: teaching the "dangerous knowledge" of practices of activism," *Canadian Journal of Development Studies/Revue canadienne d'études du développement*, 34(3), pp. 364–383.
- Jaffe, J. (2017) "Knowledge Equity is Social Justice: Engaging a Practice Theory Perspective of Knowledge for Rural Transformation," *Rural Sociology*, 82(3), pp. 391–410.
- Lipscombe, T. A., Hendrick, A., Dzidic, P. L., Garvey, D. C., & Bishop, B. (2021) "Directions for research practice in decolonising methodologies: Contending with paradox," *Methodological Innovations*, 14(1), pp. 1–11: <https://doi.org/10.1177/20597991211006288>.
- Mackenzie, J. (2008) "'Making Black Scotsmen and Scotswomen?' Scottish Missionaries and the Eastern Cape Colony in the Nineteenth Century," in H.M. Carey (Ed.), *Empires of Religion*, London: Palgrave Macmillan, pp. 113–136.
- Mackenzie, J. M., and Devine, T. (Eds.) (2011) *Scotland and the British Empire*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Maduro, O. (2011) "An(other) Invitation to Epistemological Humility: Notes toward a Self-Critical Approach to Counter-Knowledges," in Ada María Isasi-Díaz and Eduardo Mendieta (Eds.) *Decolonizing Epistemologies: Latina/o Theology and Philosophy*, New York, USA: Fordham University Press, pp. 87–104.

Matemba, Y.H. (2014) "Problems, survival and transformation: religious education in Scotland – a historical review, 1962–1992," *History of Education*, 43(4), pp. 542–560.

Matemba, Y.H. (2015) "Mismatches between legislative policy and school practice in religious education: the Scottish case," *Religious Education: The official journal of the Religious Education Association*, 110(1), pp. 70–94.

Matemba, Y.H. (2018) "Religious (and Moral) Education", in Bryce, T., Humes, W., Gillies, D., and Kennedy, A. (Eds.), *Scottish Education* (5th ed.), Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press, pp. 353–358.

Matemba, Y.H. (2021a) "Decolonising religious education in sub-Saharan Africa through the prism of anticolonialism: a conceptual proposition," *British Journal of Religious Education*, 43(1), pp. 33–45.

Matemba, Y.H. (2021b) "Religious Identity, Social Space, and Discourses of Religious Education Reform in Scotland and Malawi: A Bourdieusian Analysis", *Journal of Religious Education*, 69(2), pp. 219–238.

Matemba, Y.H. (2024) "Multi-faith RE: A Theoretical and Practical Conundrum," in L. Philip Barnes (Ed.) *Debates in Religious Education* (2nd Edition), London: Routledge, pp. 178–189.

McCarthy, A. (2022) "Bad History: The Controversy over Henry Dundas and the Historiography of the Abolition of the Slave Trade," *Scottish Affairs*, 31(2), pp. 133–153.

Mercer, J.A. (2017), Special Issue: Race, Racism, anti-Racism, and Religious Education, *Religious Education: The Official Journal of the Religious Education Association*, 112(1), 92pp.

Mignolo, M. (2000) *Local Histories/global Designs: Essays on the Coloniality of Power, Subaltern Knowledges and Border Thinking*, Princeton: Princeton University Press.

Mohammed, K. (2023) *National Anti-Racism Framework for Initial Teacher Education*, Glasgow: Scottish Council of Deans.

Quijano, A. (2000) "Coloniality of Power and Eurocentrism in Latin America" *International Sociology*, 15(2), pp. 215–232.

Race, R., Gill, D., Kaitell, E., Mahmud, A., Thorpe, a. and Kelli Wolfe, K. (2022) "Proclamations and provocations: Decolonising curriculum in education research and professional practice," *Equity in Education & Society*, 1(1), pp. 82–96.

Scholes, S. (2022) "Precarious provision and mixed messages: religious education, school inspection, and the law in Scottish non-denominational secondary schools," *British Journal of Religious Education*, 44(4), pp. 512–527.

Scottish Government (2009) Curriculum for Excellence: Religious and Moral Education, Glasgow: Scottish Education Department.

Scottish Government (2018) New Scots Refugee Integration Strategy 2018–2022, Edinburgh: Scottish Government.

Scottish Office (1992) 5–14: Religious and Moral Education, Edinburgh: Scottish Office Education Department.

Scottish Office (1994) Religious Education: Effective Teaching and Learning in Scottish Primary and Secondary School, Report by HM Inspectors of Schools, Edinburgh: Scottish Office Education Department.

Smart, N. (1968) *Secular Education and the Logic of Religion*, London: Faber & Faber.

Solomon, M. (2006), "Norms of Epistemic Diversity," *Episteme*, 3(1-2), pp. 23–36.

Sonn, C.C., Stevens, G., Duncan, N. (2013) "Decolonisation, Critical Methodologies and Why Stories Matter," in Stevens, G., Duncan, N., Hook, D. (Eds.) *Race, Memory, and the Apartheid Archive. Studies in the Psychosocial*, London: Palgrave Macmillan, pp. 294–314.

Stewart, L. (2011) Policy Letter – Curriculum for Excellence – Provision of Religious and Moral Education in Non-denominational Schools and Religious Education in Roman Catholic Schools, Learning Directorate, Curriculum Division: Scottish Government.

Trisos, C.H., Auerbach, J. and Katti, M. (2021) "Decoloniality and anti-oppressive practices for a more ethical ecology," *Nat Ecol Evol*, 5, pp. 1205–1212.

Vallejos, O., Levrant, N. and Matharan, G. (2023) "Epistemic activism and the production of spatial knowledge in Argentina," *Tapuya: Latin American Science, Technology and Society*, 6(1): 2216098: DOI: 10.1080/25729861.2023.2216098.

Vliek, M. (2019) "'It's Not Just about Faith': Narratives of Transformation When Moving Out of Islam in the Netherlands and Britain," *Islam and Christian–Muslim Relations*, 30(3), pp. 323–344.

The logo is a white circle containing the text 'UNIVERSITY OF THE WEST of SCOTLAND' in a small, black, sans-serif font. Below this, the letters 'UWS' are written in a large, bold, black, serif font. The background of the entire page is a complex geometric pattern of overlapping squares and circles in various shades of blue, from light sky blue to deep navy blue.

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